

COMBINING THERMOGRAPHIC AND LAMB WAVES INVESTIGATION DATA FOR THE CHARACTERISATION OF CFRP DELAMINATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) techniques have distinct advantages and limitations, making their selection highly dependent on factors such as the material being tested, the part geometry, the expected defects, or the experimental conditions. To address their limitations, researchers and industry professionals have widely explored ways to optimise existing NDT techniques. A promising direction is Data Fusion, extensively explored in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), which combines data from multiple inspection techniques to enhance defect detection and material characterisation.

In this study, a Data Fusion methodology is implemented to combine quantitative results from InfraRed Thermographic (IRT) inspection and Lamb Waves inspection, an advanced Ultrasonic Testing (UT) technique adapted to relatively thin structures such as plates. IRT enables rapid, non-contact detection of surface and near-surface defects through heat propagation analysis. In this work, thermal diffusivities are calculated from cooling curves extracted from thermal maps. Lamb Waves are generated and measured using a fully non-contact system; their interaction with internal defects is quantified using RMS energy values, which provide insights into subsurface damage.

However, Lamb Wave propagation in anisotropic, layered composites remains challenging, with possible misdetections. Multiple CFRP samples of varying geometries and thicknesses (1.6 mm to 6.4 mm), with artificial and impact-induced delaminations, were tested. Results showed that while each method has detection limitations, their fusion offers enhanced characterisation. This is especially valuable for complex defects such as lightning-induced delaminations or deep-layer damage.

By combining IRT's surface sensitivity and Lamb Waves' subsurface reach, the fusion approach improves not only detection but also the characterisation of damage mechanisms, crucial for composite materials with complex architectures. Future work will focus on improving individual techniques, such as refining signal processing algorithms for Lamb Waves inspection, and extending the investigated dataset to a wider range of composite structures and defects.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of Carbon Fibres Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) materials in aerospace, automotive and energy sectors has led to growing demands for highly reliable and efficient Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) techniques. Due to the complex, anisotropic and layered nature of these materials, detecting and characterising internal defects such as delaminations remains a major challenge. To address this issue, industries and researchers have been widely investigating the performance of NDT methods to improve their efficiency and accuracy and obtained major advances over the last decades. For example, the introduction of X-Ray Computed Tomography (XRCT) has transformed Radiographic Testing (RT) capabilities by supplying 3D volumetric imagery methods. The development of Phased Array Ultrasonic Testing (PAUT) or non-contact systems based on guided waves revolutionised classic Ultrasonic Testing (UT) abilities [1–3].

However, the limitations inherent to each of these methods often persist, particularly as they often come from the application cases or the CFRP materials. In this context, Data Fusion has emerged as a promising approach in the field of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). By combining data from different inspection techniques, Data Fusion aims to provide a more comprehensive and robust understanding of structural integrity. This integration can take various forms, from simple visual overlays to more advanced mathematical or statistical models that merge complementary parameters. The goal is not only to increase detection reliability, but also to enrich the interpretation of damage features by leveraging the distinct sensitivities of each technique [4–10].

This study explores the application of Data Fusion to InfraRed Thermography (IRT) and Ultrasonic Lamb Waves inspection, two NDT methods based on different physical principles. While IRT offers rapid detection of shallow discontinuities by analysing thermal response on the surface [2,11], Lamb Wave inspection enables the detection of internal defects by analysing the interaction of propagating guided ultrasonic waves with material discontinuities [12,13]. While these two techniques are particularly well-suited to thin-walled CFRP plate inspection, each of them remains subjected to physical and practical limitations when applied individually. IRT is inherently limited in depth penetration due to the thermal diffusion nature of heat propagation, and its sensitivity decreases with increasing material thickness or with defects located deep beneath the surface. Conversely, Lamb Wave inspection suffers from complex propagation behaviour in anisotropic and heterogeneous materials such as CFRPs, often leading to ambiguous or incomplete defect characterisation. Wave mode conversion, dispersion, and scattering can significantly affect signal interpretation, especially in the presence of geometrical complexity or stiffness variations [12,13].

The present work proposes a quantitative fusion approach applied to CFRP samples with known delamination features. Thermal diffusivities are extracted from IRT cooling curves, while Root Mean Square (RMS) energy values are calculated from Lamb Wave measurements to assess internal damage. The study includes a variety of sample configurations, incorporating different layups, thicknesses, and delamination types. Particular attention is paid to lightning-strike-induced delaminations, which represent a challenging case due to complex damage morphology and depth.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents the experimental samples structure and their manufacturing process, particularly the insertion of defects. Section 3 describes the experimental, data acquisition and data extraction process for the two NDT methods used in the study: IRT and UT. Section 4 details the Data Fusion methodology. The results of the study are presented and discussed in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes the study and proposes directions for future work.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES

Three types of CFRP samples were investigated in this study, as shown in Fig. 1.

The stiffened plates LW50S and LW75S are 450×450 mm² CF/epoxy laminates (T800S/3900-2B, autoclave-cured at 180 °C) with a quasi-isotropic 8-ply lay-up [45/0/-45/90]_s. A central stiffened area (100×450 mm²) was created by adding eight plies with a [-45/0/45/0]_s lay-up. Artificial delaminations were introduced by inserting a Teflon film between the base and stiffened zones, with widths of 50 mm and 75 mm for LW50S and LW75S, respectively.

The flat plates LW16 and LW32, also 450×450 mm² and made from the same CF/epoxy system, consist of 16 and 32 plies with lay-ups [45/0/-45/90]_{2s} and [45/0/-45/90]_{4s}, respectively. LW16 contains Teflon-based delaminations of various sizes (10 to 50 mm), while LW32 includes delaminations at different depths (from 8 to 24 plies).

Finally, LS1 and LS2 are 150×150 mm² plates made of plain weave carbon fabric and a conductive Polyaniline/Phenol (PDPD) resin, as described in [14], with a [0/90]₁₀ lay-up. Artificial lightning strike tests were performed using -100 kA peak current pulses, leading to surface swelling in circular areas of about 30 mm diameter. These damaged zones are later segmented into three subregions based on thermographic imaging: a black ring, a white ring, and a grey centre.

Fig. 1: Experimental samples' configuration representation (top view)

3 NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING

3.1 InfraRed Thermography (IRT)

3.1.1 Experimental system

The InfraRed Thermography system used in this study is the Active Pulse Thermography setup from Echotherm Thermal Wave Imaging [15]. It consists of a hood enclosing the inspected area, equipped with a high-energy flash lamp and a FLIR SC4000 infrared camera, connected via an umbilical cable to a mobile control unit containing the flash power source, a sample support, and a computer running MOSAIQ 4.2 analysis software.

For the inspection, the sample is positioned on the dedicated support and the hood is placed directly above it to ensure consistent illumination and thermal capture. Due to their large surface area, samples LW50S, LW75S, LW16 and LW32 were inspected in four successive scans (upper left, upper right, lower left, and lower right). A flash pulse of 30 ms is emitted for each scan, after which surface temperature evolution is recorded for a duration T_{shot} at 300 frames per second by the infrared camera. The acquired thermographic data are then post-processed to generate Thermographic Signal Reconstruction (TSR) cartographies.

In this study, log–log cooling curves were extracted at selected points across the sample surfaces from these TSR maps in order to estimate the thermal diffusivity α .

3.1.2 Data extraction

To evaluate the thermal behaviour of the CFRP samples, thermal diffusivity α was selected as the key parameter, as it reflects the material’s ability to conduct heat relative to its capacity to store it. For each sample, log–log cooling curves were extracted from TSR cartographies at selected measurement points, allowing the determination of α based on the breaking time T_{break} , based on the relation:

$$\alpha = \frac{t^2}{\exp(T_{break})} \quad (1)$$

With t the thickness of the material and T_{break} the breaking time of the cooling curve, as shown in the Fig. 2.

The measurement points are selected for each sample depending on their configuration, in order to compare thermal behaviour in different zones such as delaminated zones and healthy zones, or zones of different thicknesses. On the stiffened samples (LW50S and LW75S), measurement points were positioned in zones of varying thickness (8-ply, 16-ply) and above the artificial delamination, with twelve and ten points respectively. For the small delamination plates (LW16 and LW32), sixteen points were selected across healthy areas and Teflon-inserted defect zones. Finally, on the lightning-strike-damaged samples (LS1 and LS2), the analysis focused on four distinct zones identified from the TSR images and represented in Fig.1: the healthy background, a peripheral “black ring”, an intermediate “white ring”, and a central “grey zone.”

Fig. 2 shows an example of IRT results obtained from this method for LW75S sample, with a) the localisation of measurement points (different colours and shapes representing different zones of interest), b) the log-log curves extracted from each of these measurement point with an example of determination of T_{break} and c) the thermal diffusivities obtained from equation (1) using the measured T_{break} . In all cases, thermal diffusivity values were calculated with associated uncertainties, using a recording duration $T_{shot} = 9.3$ s and a frame rate of 300 fps. This localised quantification of α enables the identification of material heterogeneities and delamination-affected areas, offering a more informative characterisation than surface temperature mapping alone. Fig. 3 shows the thermal diffusivities calculated for all measurement points of each sample, along with a localisation of these points.

Fig. 2: IRT data obtained for sample LW75S with a) measurement points localisation, b) log-log curves with demonstration of T_{break} and c) thermal diffusivities calculated

Fig.3: Results of IRT data for all experimental samples

3.2 Lamb Waves

3.2.1 Experimental system

This study uses a fully non-contact system to extract Lamb Wave propagation data from the experimental samples. The excitation is performed using a Laser Induced Plasma Shock Wave (LIPSW) setup, based on a SURELITE III-10 Nd:YAG laser (5 ns pulse, 1064 nm wavelength, 9.5 mm beam diameter, 850 mJ energy), focused through a plano-convex lens. At a standoff distance $d = 10$ mm from the surface, a plasma is generated and the associated shock waves, encountering the surface, are the source of Lamb Waves propagation along the experimental plate. The response is measured using a

Scanning Laser Doppler Vibrometer (SLDV). For samples LW50S, LW75S, LW16 and LW32, a Polytec PSV-500 system (He-Ne laser, 0–20 m/s velocity range) was used, while the new-generation Polytec Q-tec system was employed for LS1 and LS2. The experimental setup used in this study has been widely described in [13].

3.2.2 Data extraction

Lamb Wave propagation was measured over predefined zones on each sample using point-by-point acquisition with the SLDV system. For the stiffened samples (LW50S and LW75S), a 200×200 mm² central area was scanned with a 2 mm spatial step in both directions, resulting in 10,201 points, each recorded over 0.8 ms at 2.56 MHz. The resulting data formed a matrix of 10,201 columns (measurement points) by 2048 rows (time samples). For the flat plates (LW16 and LW32), the scanned area was extended to 400×400 mm² to cover nearly the entire surface, using the same 2 mm spatial resolution. Each point was recorded over 1.6 ms at 3.125 MHz, resulting in matrices of 40,401 points \times 5000 time samples. For the lightning strike samples (LS1 and LS2), the scanned area was set to 140×140 mm², again with 2 mm resolution. Signals were recorded for 1 ms at 3.125 MHz, yielding matrices of 5041 columns \times 3125 rows.

To quantify the signal energy at each point, the Root Mean Square (RMS) value was computed using the standard formula:

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n S_i^2} \quad (2)$$

Where S_i is the signal amplitude at time step i , and n is the total number of time samples.

The RMS values represent the average energy of the Lamb Wave signal at each surface point. High RMS values may indicate energy concentration due to reflections, scattering from defects, or local changes in wave amplitude, potentially linked to delaminations or thickness variations. Conversely, low RMS values suggest attenuation or limited interaction with structural features. These values are mapped across the scanned areas to generate RMS cartographies, shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: RMS cartographies obtained for all experimental samples

4 DATA FUSION

Data fusion is a powerful approach for integrating multiple sources of information to enhance the reliability and interpretability of defect detection. In this study, a feature-level fusion strategy is used, inspired by similar approaches in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). The goal is to combine the quantitative outputs from InfraRed Thermography (thermal diffusivity α) and Lamb Wave inspection (RMS energy) to enable a richer characterisation of the inspected CFRP samples [4–10].

The method consists of plotting the thermal diffusivity values (obtained from IRT) against the RMS values (extracted from Lamb Wave measurements) in 2D scatter plots, with each point representing a measurement location on the sample. This bivariate representation allows the emergence of clusters corresponding to different zones or damage types. In contrast to a single-parameter analysis, the combined view enhances the separation between structural states that may not be distinguishable using one method alone. This is particularly useful when one modality provides ambiguous information due to physical limitations (e.g., depth sensitivity in IRT or propagation noise in Lamb Waves).

The results of the data fusion process are presented and discussed in the following section.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data fusion results are shown in Fig. 5 for LW50S, LW75S, LW16 and LW32, and in Fig. 6 for LS1 and LS2. In LW50S and LW75S, measurement points were grouped into three zones: i) 8-ply healthy areas, ii) 16-ply healthy areas, and iii) delaminated areas in the stiffened region.

Thermal diffusivity was calculated point-by-point from IRT data, while RMS values were averaged per zone due to the smaller acquisition area of Lamb Wave scans. Fig. 5 shows a clear separation of these three groups. Interestingly, the 8-ply zones split into two clusters depending on their position relative to the wave excitation point. This difference, captured only by Lamb Waves, illustrates that signal amplitude is influenced not only by the local structure but also by the path of propagation through the delamination.

In LW16 and LW32, 16 points were analysed across healthy and defective areas with varying defect sizes (10–50 mm) and depths (8–24 plies). As shown in Fig. 5, the fusion reveals only a weak separation between healthy and damaged zones. The Lamb Waves data show a slight drop in RMS for delaminated regions, but no clear differentiation is observed across different defect sizes or depths. This highlights a limitation of both methods when applied to small or subtle delaminations.

The damage in LS1 and LS2 exhibits a visible surface deformation and distinct thermal patterns in IRT. Based on the thermographic images, four zones were identified: healthy background, black ring, white ring, and grey centre. Using the same zone segmentation, the scatter plot in Fig. 6 shows that fusion enables a clearer distinction between zones than either method alone. For example, Lamb Waves can separate the grey centre from the healthy background, while IRT alone could not, likely due to thickness variations. Conversely, IRT captures distinct behaviour in the black ring, which is poorly resolved by Lamb Waves due to its narrow geometry and possible interference effects.

IRT provides information about surface-level heat diffusion, while Lamb Waves probe internal mechanical properties through guided wave propagation. In the stiffened and lightning-strike samples, the combination of both offers complementary insights:

- (i) IRT resolves thickness variations and localised heating effects,
- (ii) Lamb Waves highlight stiffness reductions due to delaminations.

In contrast, both methods struggle with small artificial delaminations, where signal changes are less pronounced and easily masked by measurement noise or geometric variability.

The apparent increase in thermal diffusivity in thicker areas, despite α being theoretically independent of thickness, is likely due to heat conduction through the metal support base. As thickness increases, thermal losses to the base decrease, leading to artificially higher α values. This phenomenon is especially visible in LW50S and LW75S and must be considered when interpreting thermal data.

In the lightning strike samples, the extreme energy conditions cause local material transformations such as carbonisation, porosity or microcracking which significantly alter both thermal and mechanical responses. This explains the high diffusivity observed in the black ring and the strong Lamb Wave scattering in the central defect.

Finally, the study demonstrates that the data fusion approach effectively compensates for the limitations of each method, providing a more nuanced picture of the internal damage, particularly in complex or multi-zone configurations.

Fig. 5: Data fusion results for LW50S, LW75S, LW16 and LW32 (from top to bottom)

Fig. 6: Data fusion results for LS1 and LS2 (top to bottom)

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, the combination of InfraRed Thermography (IRT) and Ultrasonic Lamb Wave inspection through a data fusion approach for the characterisation of delaminations in CFRP composites has been investigated. Each technique, based on distinct physical principles, offers valuable yet partial insight into the material's condition: IRT is sensitive to surface and near-surface thermal behaviour, while Lamb Waves provide information related to internal mechanical changes. However, both face limitations when used independently, particularly in cases involving complex geometries, variable thicknesses, or subtle defect signatures.

By jointly analysing thermal diffusivity (from IRT) and RMS energy (from Lamb Waves) through feature-level fusion, the proposed method enabled a more comprehensive interpretation of damage patterns. The results demonstrated a clear benefit for samples with complex internal structures, especially stiffened panels and lightning-strike-induced damage, where single-method inspections either failed to differentiate certain zones or produced ambiguous data.

In contrast, the fusion method was less effective for small artificial delaminations, where both techniques showed limited sensitivity to variations in size or depth. These results suggest that the approach remains dependent on the physical detectability of the defect by at least one modality, and that further improvements are needed in signal acquisition and processing to enhance sensitivity to fine-scale

damage.

Beyond the immediate results, this study highlights the potential of multimodal NDT as a step towards more quantitative and integrated material characterisation. Moving beyond binary “healthy/defect” classifications, data fusion offers a promising avenue for future inspection strategies in complex composite structures, with applications in both quality control and structural health monitoring. Further work will aim to refine the methodology, explore alternative fusion strategies, and extend the study to more complex configurations and real-world defect scenarios.

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